

Sustainable Urban Clean Water Governance in Indonesia: Problems, Institutions, and Future Solutions

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Abstract

This study aims to explain the urban community-based clean water provision in Bandung City, in terms of general problems, institutional and governance aspects. Community-based clean water governance should be developed so that communities are independent and ready to produce clean water. When clean water is available, the time and money spent on obtaining clean water can be used for other more productive purposes and can improve community welfare. The method used in this research is a qualitative approach with a descriptive approach. Data collection was done through literature review, in-depth interviews and several site surveys. The results of this study indicate the low performance of Regional Water Supply Company in managing clean water supply and the absence of local regulations related to urban community-based clean water governance. In addition, the implementation of clean water provision in Bandung City has not integrated community-based governance. The conclusion of this research is that urban clean water governance in Bandung City and other cities in Indonesia using a community-based system for the current condition is very relevant. Furthermore, it is important to draft a local regulation on urban community-based water governance that aims to protect water resources as well as to create a clean and healthy environment, and sustainable.

Keywords: *sustainable, water supply, governance, urban.*

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Introduction

The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in 2002 stated in its General Comment No. 15, expressly interpreting article 11 and article 12 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, that the right to water is inseparable from other human rights. In its argument, the Committee pointed out that many other human rights would not be available to people if the right to water was not recognized before. The right to life, the right to food, the right to maintain health levels are rights that in order to be fulfilled require the right to water - as a prerequisite. It is stated that water is not only needed for drinking but is also an integral part of food processing, or the creation of healthy housing conditions and other human needs for life. It even goes so far as to assert that the committee

places an obligation on states to guarantee the right to water for every citizen (UN Economic and Social Council, 2003).

Water demand in Indonesia will continue to increase in line with population growth. The National Development Planning Agency (Bappenas) estimates that water demand will continue to increase, one of which is for household and urban needs. The following is a projection of annual water demand by sector until 2045 in Indonesia (Danareksa Research Institute, 2023).

Figure 1. Indonesia's Projected Water Demand by Sector (until 2045)

On the other hand, the availability of clean water has reached around 60 percent (Suryani, 2016). This means that there are still 40 percent or around 90 million Indonesians forced to use water that is not suitable for health for daily life. In comparison with several other countries in Southeast Asia, until 2020 the percentage of rural area access to water sources in Indonesia is still much lower than several neighboring countries. Malaysia is the highest in Southeast Asia with the level of access to water sources in rural areas reaching 94 percent. In Indonesia, this figure only reaches the level of 69 percent, lower than Vietnam which has reached 72 percent.

A number of problems generally surround water governance in Indonesia, such as the uneven distribution of water services, water pollution, the government's inability to expand irrigation networks for agricultural purposes, and reduced supply of clean and drinking water due to the reduction of water catchment areas due to land conversion. In terms of distribution, it appears to be more focused on serving commercial activities that support economic development (Pristiandarum 2023). Only consumers who can afford to pay can have access to clean water. Meanwhile, water pollution can be seen as rivers in Java, which are the source of water for the community, for bathing, washing, and as a raw source of processed drinking water, are generally in poor condition due to pollution from industrial waste and domestic waste (Dawud et.al. 2016).

In addition, the quality of open water sources in Indonesia is still limited as reflected in the water quality index which is at a moderate level. In 2022, the water quality index in Indonesia was recorded at 53.88. This score indicates that there is still domestic pollution in rivers and other open water sources in various regions (Danareksa Research Institute, 2023).

Figure 2. Indonesia's Water Quality Index (in percent)

In terms of water sources, groundwater dominates the springs used daily. Excessive use of groundwater has the potential to cause several problems, such as land subsidence, saltwater intrusion, and deterioration of water quality as it is susceptible to pollution. The use of piped water (Regional Water Supply Companies and similar companies) is quite low and mostly concentrated in urban areas. This is influenced by limited piped water distribution infrastructure to rural areas as well as the economy (Danareksa Research Institute, 2023).

Figure 3. Indonesia's Water Use Resource (in percent)

Surface and ground water sources governance should be focused on prioritizing demand and utilization, adequate water allocation, and implementation of water conservation. In addition to improving the sustainability of clean water availability, public awareness is needed in preserving the environment in general at water sources in particular. Participation at the source includes maintaining quality, quantity, and continuity by saving water usage, increasing water utilization, maintaining water catchment areas, controlling water pollution, protecting and preserving water sources, and managing water quality (Permatasari et al., 2018). Therefore, community participation in water governance is also very necessary.

Bandung City as one of the cities in Indonesia and the capital of the West Java province with a total population of 2,468,163 people (Statistics Indonesia, 2023) and with an area of 16,729 ha is currently experiencing a clean water crisis at several points in the Bandung City area. One of the causes of the clean water crisis is the lack of public access to clean water. The lack of clean water that can be accessed by the community can cause various diseases. One of the diseases caused as a result of the difficulty of access to clean water is diarrhea experienced by a number of toddlers in the Bandung city.

Similar to other urban communities, the main source of clean water for most people in Bandung City is the Regional Drinking Water Company. Since the Dutch colonial era until the mid-1970s, Tirtawening Regional Water Company was able to fulfill all the clean water needs of its citizens. In fact, the clean water supply from the Regional Drinking Water Company can be enjoyed by almost all city residents continuously for 24 hours. However, those good times are a distant memory.

As the population growth rate increases and the city expands, the Tirtawening Regional Water Company is currently only able to serve 53 percent of the total population with a service of around 60 liters/person/day of the population's clean water needs. This means that there are still 1,254,036 people in Bandung who have not received clean water distribution, so they have to look for other water sources such as from wells or get it from itinerant water vendors.

In order to provide clean water networks in urban areas, communities need to be encouraged to be more independent. The government only plays a role as a standard setter, facilitator to accommodate the aspirations of citizens related to clean water service issues and improve the quality of water production and access to services to the public. This research is intended to provide alternative solutions in sustainable urban community-based clean water governance.

Methods

The method used in this study is a qualitative method with a descriptive approach, which means qualitative methods is "a type of research that explores and understands a group of people stemming from a social problem." (Creswell, 2016). Data collection in this study will begin with a literature review of some statistical data relevant to the study, some reports of other studies related to the objectives and content of this study, including the results of the analysis of regional units and regional ecosystems that manage community-based clean water.

Furthermore, several site surveys were conducted to estimate all the direct and indirect use values of the community-based clean water governance areas. In this context, the research method in the site survey was the rapid rural appraisal method, which focused, among others, on information and data from all stakeholders who utilize community-based clean water. In addition, to capture more accurate information, an in-depth interview technique was also conducted. The best possible informant retrieval technique used a survey technique combined with a snow-bowling technique. Where, respondents will be determined based on previous respondents. This is intended to create a deeper connection between the status and characteristics of one respondent and another.

Results

This section will explain the results and discussion related to sustainable urban water governance in Indonesia, especially in Bandung City. Some of the sub-chapters described are: existing conditions of water governance, the role of stakeholders in water governance, and community-based water supply governance in Bandung City.

Water Supply Governance Problems

Tirtawening Water Supply Company of Bandung City is a regional company that manages water. The position of water, in the constitution, is a good that controls the lives of many people, and is even a social good. In such a philosophical position, the state has the right to manage it in order to achieve justice in its use. From the perspective of market structure, the Tirtawening Water Supply Company is a company that falls under the term natural monopoly. That is why the government manages it in a regulated manner. Because of these characteristics, the result is that the Tirtawening Water Supply Company is often not/not for profit but to create maximum benefits for stakeholders.

Currently, the Tirtawening Water Supply Company is still needed by the people in Bandung City to fulfill the need for clean water that is suitable for consumption. The presence of Tirtawening Water Supply Company is made possible through Law No. 5 of 1962 as a regional company owned by the local government. The function of Tirtawening Water Supply Company is to provide services and organize public benefits in the field of clean water. While its activities, namely: collecting, treating, purifying and then distributing to customers.

Based on population data (Statistics Indonesia, 2023) the total population of Bandung at the end of 2021, 2022 and 2023 is 2,292,016; 2,315,895; and 2,340,624, respectively, with growth rates varying between 1.0% and 2.9% over the period. With a projected average growth rate of 1.7% per year, it is estimated that the population of Bandung will be 2,380,883 in 2007. During the period 2021 - 2023, the service coverage of the city's water supply company has increased from 57.6% in 2021 to 63.8% in 2023.

The conveyance system mostly uses a gravity system. The use of pumps is only one buster pump unit to push the flow around the margahayu housing. The distribution system carried out so far to meet community water needs is by direct connection, public taps and water terminals. At this time the operating hours of the clean water production system run for 24 hours, unless there is a disturbance in the intake system which usually occurs during the rainy season, especially at the Bantar Awi intake for the Dago Pakar Air Treatment Plant. The duration of flow in the distribution system is on average 15 hours per day, where turns are still taken in most service areas, this is due to the limitations of the network hydraulic system which is also caused by the limited discharge of clean water production.

Water production for the last three years is 79.9 million m³ in 2021, 79.3 million m³ in 2022, and 84.8 million m³ in 2023. During this time, Tirtawening Water Supply Company only uses existing sources, and does not purchase water from other parties. In line with the decrease in the amount of water produced in the period 2021 - 2023, the amount of water distributed also experienced a slight decrease in that period, from 76.7 million m³ in 2021 to 76.3 million m³ in 2022. The amount of water distributed increased again in 2023 to 81.5 million m³. This is due to the additional capacity of 100 l/sec from springs in North Bandung and East Bandung (springs: Ciwangi, Lebak Baygon, Panyairan, and Pasir Impun, and an additional 30 l/sec from deep wells in AW11 and Gempol Asri.

The main problems faced by the Tirtawening Water Supply Company according to data in the 2022 Company Performance Improvement Plan are: (a) Limited production capacity. The current condition of several existing water treatment plants does not operate in accordance with their design capacity. (b) Low volume of water recorded in customer meters. The low volume of water recorded in customer meters affects the water loss rate. (c) Inaccurate data on the volume of distributed water. (d) Leaks in the

pipings network. Distribution pipes installed in the service area of the Tirtawening Water Supply Company are generally old, even along 186 km of *Asbestos* Cement Pipe (asbestos) type distribution pipes that are prone to leakage. (e) The incomplete implementation of the service pipe removal program in pipe and the implementation of ex-subscription cover. The condition of service pipes installed in the field is still located behind the house, making it difficult to read meters and monitor illegal water usage. Currently, the Tirtawening Water Supply Company is still carrying out the removal of customer service pipes in path and rechecking ex-subscribers. (f) Inaccurate subscription data. The billing system has not been optimized, resulting in the mutation of subscription data that has not been managed properly. And (g) Illegal connection/illegal water usage. Based on field checks, there are still ex-customers who legally use water from the Tirtawening Water Supply Company. (h) Less raw water discharge.

Limited availability of raw water both in quantity and quality, where in the dry season the quantity of water from the Cikapundung river, Cipanjal, springs decreased while in the rainy season there were changes in quality, especially high turbidity in the Cipanjal, Cibeureum and Cikapundung rivers. Although there have been programs from the Central Government and West Java Province, through the Department of Water Resources, until now there has been no more concrete effort to increase capacity through the construction of reservoirs. One of the simultaneous programs of the Tirtawening Water Supply Company is to contribute to the conservation of water resources. (i) Transmission system capability is declining. The condition of the existing transmission pipelines is generally old, located on roads, residential areas and prone to leakage. In addition, the transmission pipes cannot deliver water according to their design capacity, resulting in "idle capacity" at the Badak Singa Water Treatment Plant. Likewise, the availability of transmission pipe equipment is limited so that if a pipe breaks, it takes longer to repair it. (j) The quality of borehole water is not up to standard. In general, the quality of existing borehole water has high levels of Fe and Mn that require treatment, but the resulting water capacity tends to decrease, resulting in high operational costs.

Future Stakeholder Roles

Clean water governance can be carried out by the Central Government, Local Government, private sector or community, either individually or jointly (Nanda et al., 2023). Clean water governance by the community can be carried out by individuals, groups of people including customary law communities, professional groups, interest groups, and legal entities. These components are stakeholders in clean water governance.

Clean water governance, which is complex and involves the interests of many sectors, requires the support of a strong and structured institutional system (Saribanon et al., 2023). In terms of its functions, the institutional system in clean water can be simply disaggregated according to its function, which consists of five elements, firstly, Regulator or Government, which is the decision-making institution, in this case the officials who are authorized to set policies/decisions (for example in the Region are: Governor, Regent/Mayor and the Heads of related Departments/Agencies that are subordinate to them (Christianingsih, 2018).

The roles played by stakeholders who have the authority to take or make decision-making policies are: a) Formulate legal products and rules of the game (such as norms, standards, guidelines, instructions and criteria) relating to the role and involvement of communities in decision-making for clean water governance; b) Revise existing policies at the national, regional and local levels that do not favor the welfare of the wider community; c) Conduct a review or assessment of the ability of all public officials related to clean water governance to be followed up with capacity building or reassignment to appropriate positions (fit and proper); d) Provide political commitment, especially for the legislature and executive, in making clean water governance policies in favor of community welfare; e) Improving the capacity of existing human resources, both professionals, bureaucrats and community members to be better able to manage water supply in a sustainable manner; f) Developing communication between stakeholders

through various media that have been mastered and those that have not been mastered by community members; g) Encourage assistance to more appropriate targets, namely local communities, such as encouraging block grants from the city government to villages; h) Conducting socio-cultural and economic studies in community-based clean water governance to inform stakeholders; i) Developing awareness about community-based clean water governance through various efforts, such as simplifying the concept and mechanism of managing infrastructure and water supply so that it can be understood and comprehended by residents or community forums, developing and legalizing community forums.

Secondly, Operator, which is an institution that is formed and functions to carry out the daily operation or governance of clean water governance and existing infrastructure in an area or area unit, for example a Business Entity or a kind of Clean Water Supply Company for water governance in a network of water sources or other community business units (Munawaroh et al., 2020). This institution was formed by the Regulator, with the main task of carrying out the regulator's decision in providing clean water supply services to the community.

The roles played by stakeholders who have an interest in making activities/policies run well and smoothly in clean water governance are: a) Make efforts to institutionalize the process of community participation or involvement; b) Socializing community participation or involvement; c) Establish channels and nodes of participation; d) Exploring and considering local values and wisdom; e) Disseminating best practices; f) Strengthening methods and geographic information systems;

Thirdly, Developer, which is an institution that functions to carry out the construction of clean water infrastructure and facilities both from government elements (e.g. Project Implementing Agency, State-Owned Enterprises, Regional-Owned Enterprises) and non-government institutions (investors). The role of this institution is especially needed when there is an imbalance between the demand or need for water and the ability to provide water (Umayasari et al., 2022).

The roles performed by stakeholders who carry out infrastructure development are: a) Conducting various efforts to sensitize various stakeholders on the essence of providing clean water that is suitable for drinking by prioritizing sustainable development; b) Conducting campaigns on transparency and accountability in community-based clean water governance; c) Conducting socialization and mediation of the community-based clean water governance process; d) Conducting profitable efforts in community-based clean water governance, such as through pilot projects or similar activities.

Fourth, User or Beneficiary, which includes all elements of society which are also seen as basic rights, namely the community as beneficiaries must respond to all external interventions that affect their lives, both individuals and community groups that benefit directly or indirectly from clean water governance services (Siswanto et al., 2021).

The roles performed by stakeholders who receive benefits are: e) Encourage the development of community forums; f) Seeking to obtain greater benefits from the governance of clean water that covers its area; g) Seeking to minimize conflicts in the provision of clean water with an orientation towards profit and community welfare; h) Conducting proper supervision of clean water provision by stakeholders has an interest so that activities/policies run well and smoothly in clean water governance; i) Revive the function of supervision and guardian angel in community-based clean water governance;

Finally, the Coordination Forum, which functions to receive, absorb and channel the aspirations and complaints of all elements of stakeholders (Mbusa et al., 2021). This is a representative body that is tasked with providing input to regulators as well as preparing resolutions and recommendations for solving water governance problems. Membership of this body consists of government and non-government elements in equal numbers on the basis of representation.

Community Based Clean Water Governance

The main condition or prerequisite in community-based water supply is participatory, which encourages the participation of local communities in the planning process of community-based clean water governance for their own needs as part of efforts to build a sense of ownership of the clean water infrastructure to be built (Putri et al., 2023). Communities in the target location, represented by local community representatives, accompanied by facilitators and technical assistants hold deliberations to decide on the proposed clean water infrastructure that suits their needs, local conditions, and available funds.

The standards, criteria or quantities are the local needs and conditions as well as the availability of funds allocated to the area along with the community's own contribution. The design of the water supply system here is a communal system, not an individual one, and uses appropriate technology. The focus of the study in addition to the reliability of its performance, is the ease and low cost of operation and maintenance of the water supply system for the community, so that it is expected that its utilization will be sustainable.

In an effort to ensure the sustainable utilization of clean water infrastructure, the governance of built infrastructure should be carried out by the user community itself (Dorojati et al., 2016). To be able to create a community-based governance mechanism, especially in the clean water sector, the governance of built clean water infrastructure is carried out by Local Community Organizations - Clean Water, Cooperatives and Clean Water User and Beneficiary Groups.

Local Community Organization - Clean Water is the representative body of a clean water service area, a generic name for an institution at the community level, which is a democratic forum and a forum for the highest decision-making process that reflects the aspirations of the clean water user community (Saputra et al., 2024).

Cooperatives are business entities consisting of individuals or cooperative legal entities by basing their activities on cooperative principles as well as a people's economic movement based on family principles (Nurjannah et al., 2024). The functions and roles of the Cooperative are: (a) Building and developing the potential and economic capacity of members in particular and society in general to improve their economic and social welfare; (b) Participating actively in efforts to improve the quality of human and community life; (c) Strengthening the people's economy as the basis for the strength and resilience of the national economy with cooperatives as its pillar; (d) Striving to realize and develop a national economy which is a joint business based on family principles and economic democracy.

The Clean Water User and Beneficiary Group is the implementing or managing body of a Clean Water service whose members are appointed by the Local Community Organization - Clean Water or Cooperative, consisting of people who have the expertise needed in the implementation of Clean Water provision (Fitaloka & Juwita, 2024). At the project implementation stage, the Clean Water User and Beneficiary Group can function as the executor/service provider. For work that requires special expertise, the Water User Group can work with contractors. At the operational and utilization stage, the Clean Water User and Beneficiary Group is responsible for the operational utilization, governance and sustainability of the built Clean Water infrastructure by carrying out governance functions, technical functions, and administrative functions.

Discussion

Water resources play a very important role in population, social and economic development because the provision of clean water is one of the sustainable issues, which must be able to meet the needs of today's society without ignoring or sacrificing the fulfillment of needs for future generations. The increase in

population results in an increase in the amount of demand for water resources which makes the availability of clean water decreases (Armadi et al., 2019). Areas with high population density, especially big cities, have a high potential to face the problem of clean water crisis due to the influence of urbanization, population growth and economic development.

This increase is due to increased household activity, which makes the importance of clean water availability even more important, if not managed properly it can lead to scarcity (Permata et al., 2024). In reality, some parts of the world's population do not have access to clean water. Achieving equal and universal access to safe and affordable drinking water is required as a key objective of government policy by implementing integrated water resources governance, including through inter-regional cooperation (Mustikawati, 2022).

The problem of water resource availability is influenced by two factors, namely, natural factors and human factors (Harianja, 2020). Natural factors that influence this quantity of water sourced from the ground (groundwater) have better quality and long sustainability. The availability of groundwater can be greatly influenced by 2 (two) factors, namely meteorological conditions or rainfall and geologically or where groundwater is stored or aquifer parameters. Meteorological rainfall conditions are influenced by geographical location with respect to latitude. Another factor that causes limited water resources is the human factor. These human factors include, among others, the erection of buildings without permits, an increase in the amount of waste, and forest destruction such as tree felling, forest land clearing, and illegal mining (Febriarta et al., 2024).

Efficient water utilization and ensuring the availability of clean water is necessary to prevent water scarcity, and reduce the number of populations affected by water scarcity. In determining the availability of water, both public and private managers need to obtain the value of water and determine the appropriate price, currently the pricing mechanism is divided into: (a) Supply-side strategies, focusing on balancing investment and return on water supply services; and (b) Demand-side strategies, focusing on establishing the value of water use for customers at a given price, or reflecting the ability to pay for water supply services (Armadi et al., 2019).

Noting the serious impacts of inefficient and ineffective water governance, we the Government have issued Presidential Instruction of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1/ 2024 on the acceleration of drinking water provision (Cabinet Secretariat of the Republic of Indonesia, 2024). The issuance of this Presidential Instruction is intended to realize the basic rights of the community to improve the level of public welfare, improve the quality of public health related to waterborne infectious diseases, reduce the incidence of disease and prevent stunted growth, and reduce the rate of exploitation of groundwater by the community.

The presence of the Presidential Instruction on Drinking Water has another strategic role in creating social transformation at the community level. In addition, clean water is an important factor for community sustainability (Yunita, et.al. 2020). Furthermore, the provision of water through pipelines to homes and public facilities can certainly improve the quality of drinking water consumed by the community. The distribution of drinking water allows the central government, local governments, and Regional Water Companies to monitor water quality. This is certainly different if people rely on groundwater, because the quality of the water cannot be monitored and is vulnerable to contamination with bacteria and other factors that can endanger human health (Cakti, 2024).

Conclusion

From the result and discussion, several conclusions are obtained: firstly, the low performance of Tirtawening Water Supply Company in the governance of clean water supply and the absence of local

regulations related to urban community-based clean water governance in Bandung City. Secondly, the implementation of clean water supply in Bandung City has not integrated community-based governance and regional units, and Thirdly, the implementation of clean water governance has not been carried out in a participatory manner so that the existing infrastructure for clean water supply is less cared for by the community, on the other hand the community wants participation from planning to operations.

Based on these conclusions, several things that need to be addressed in urban community-based clean water supply governance in Bandung City are as follows (a) Strive for community-based clean water governance with an area unit system because in terms of population density, groundwater depth, soil type and socioeconomic conditions of the community as well as the level of community perception and participation, an area unit-based system for current conditions is very relevant. (b) Develop a local regulation on urban community or area unit-based water governance that aims to protect water resources as well as to create a clean and healthy environment. (c) Accommodate the role of mentoring by academics and NGOs in order to increase community participation in community-based clean water governance in an area unit. And (d) Seeking alternative financing outside the local budget through a combination of government, private sector and community.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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